

A Clinicopathological Study of Pleural Effusion at ASMC, FirozabadSingh Yogesh Kumar¹, Arya Shubhangee², Tripathi Jayati³, Bandil Sonali⁴, Singh Shruti⁵, Husain Naushad⁶¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh³First Year DM Oncopathology Resident, GCRI, Ahmedabad, Gujarat⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh⁵Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, ASMC, Lalitpur, Uttar Pradesh⁶Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pleural effusion is an excessive accumulation of fluid in the pleural space. Pleural effusion is not a disease entity per se rather it's a manifestation of a complication of the pulmonary or non-pulmonary diseases. The causes of Pleural Effusion are too many. Pleural fluid analysis by cytology and cell block remain the mainstays for diagnosing etiology of pleural effusion.

Objectives: This study aimed to perform cytological analysis of pleural fluid to find out its etiology and to find prevalence of these etiologies with respect to age and sex.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was carried out at tertiary care hospital of ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh on 100 patients of Pleural Effusion coming to the Department of Pathology for cytological analysis of the Pleural fluid over a period of 1 year from January 2023 to December 2023.

Results: Out of total 100 cases of pleural effusion studied, our study found Tuberculosis to be the most common cause of pleural effusion in Firozabad region (82%) followed by malignancies in which most common was Lung Adenocarcinoma (8%) followed by Carcinoma breast (2%) and Ovarian Adenocarcinoma.

Conclusion: Most common cause of pleural effusion in Firozabad region is Tuberculosis followed by malignant pleural effusion.

Keywords: Pleural effusion, Pleural fluid Cytology, cell block, Tuberculosis, Malignant pleural effusion.

Abbreviations: Pap staining=Papanicolaou staining; ZN staining= Ziehl Nelson staining TLC=Total leucocyte count; LDH= Lactate dehydrogenase; TB= Tuberculosis.

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Introduction

Pleural space is a thin cavity between the visceral and parietal pleural layers surrounding the lungs. Normally, there is around 10 to 20 ml of pleural fluid in this space and this fluid gets continuously reabsorbed via lymphatics in the parietal pleura [1]. The pleural fluid acts as a lubricant and allows the visceral and parietal layers of the pleura to glide smoothly past each other during respiration. Pleural effusion is an excessive accumulation of fluid in the pleural spaces. Pleural effusion is not a disease entity per se rather its a manifestation of a complication of the pulmonary or nonpulmonary disease. The causes of Pleural Effusion are enormous. It is classified broadly into exudative and transudative based on Light's criteria [2]. Congestive cardiac failure is the most common cause of transudative Pleural Effusion worldwide [2]. Common causes of exudative pleural effusion include pulmonary infections, such as tuberculosis, pneumonia, malignancies, inflammatory disorders

such as pancreatitis, lupus, and rheumatoid arthritis; postcardiac injury syndrome, chylothorax, hemothorax, post-coronary artery bypass grafting (post-CABG), and benign asbestos pleural effusion.

Less common causes of pleural effusion include pulmonary embolism (exudative or transudative), drug-induced reactions (exudative), radiotherapy (exudative), esophageal rupture (exudative), and ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (exudative) [1]. Drugs commonly associated with pleural effusion development include methotrexate, amiodarone, phenytoin, and dasatinib. [1]. Pleural fluid analysis by cytology and cell block remain the mainstays for diagnosing etiology of pleural effusion [3]. Cytological examination also helps in staging and prognostication of disease apart from diagnosis especially in malignant effusions, for example, the presence of malignant effusion in lung cancer eliminates the possibility of surgical treatment and

it implies an advanced disease, short survival and hence poor prognosis in tumors of other organs as well. Cytopathologic analysis has a high diagnostic value in malignant pleural effusions [4,5].

Hence, such a study was highly required in a region like Firozabad, where Tuberculosis is quite prevalent and malignancies are also common.

Objectives:

1. To perform cytological analysis of pleural fluid to find out its etiology.
2. To find prevalence of these etiologies with respect to age and sex.

Material and Methods:

This cross-sectional study was carried out at tertiary care hospital of ASMC, Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh on 100 patients of Pleural Effusion coming to the Department of Pathology for cytological analysis of the Pleural fluid over a period of 1 year from January 2023 to December 2023.

Inclusion Criteria: All the patients whose pleural fluid samples were sent to the Department of Pathology ,ASMC, Firozabad for cytological analysis, were included in this study after obtaining consent.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who did not give consent were excluded from our study.

Ethical Approval: We conducted this study after getting ethical clearance from the institutional ethical committee.

We took detailed history of each patient, then after clinico-radiological examination(like chest X-ray PA view), we performed following routine investigations in our laboratory:-

- 1) Hemoglobin
- 2) TLC
- 3) DLC
- 4) ESR
- 5) Random blood sugar
- 6) Serum proteins
- 7) Serum LDH

On Pleural fluid, we performed:-

- 1) Fluid protein
- 2) Fluid sugar
- 3) Total Leucocyte Count of pleural fluid

4) Pleural fluid LDH level

These tests helped us categorize pleural effusions as exudative or transudative.

5) After centrifuging the fluid at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, we prepared slides from the sediment and examined it under microscope for Differential Leucocyte Count and cytomorphology after staining with GIEMSA and PAP stain.

6) We also prepared cell block and performed H&E stain.

We examined the cytosmears and cell block sections microscopically.

7) Besides above tests, we will also did ZN staining of all the smears and also Culture & Sensitivity was sent to Department of Microbiology wherever needed.

Statistical Analysis:

Data analysis was done using SPSS software & the results were analysed.

Results:

Out of 100 cases of pleural effusion ,exudative pleural effusion was found to be far more common than transudative pleural effusions(97% vs 3%). We also found that males outnumbered females by 24% (62% male cases vs 38% female cases). Male:female ratio was found to be 1.63:1. The most common cause of pleural effusion in the present study was found to be Tuberculosis of which a total of 82 cases were found (82%) among which 52 were males and 30 were females. The second most common cause in our study was malignant pleural effusions (12%) among which most common cause was Adenocarcinoma lung (8%) of which 7 were males and 1 was female ,followed by Carcinoma breast (2%) ,followed by 1 case each of Carcinoma ovary and B-cell Acute lymphoblastic Lymphoma. The third most common cause was found to be parapneumonic effusion (2%). 1 case of pleural effusion was found to be due to Rheumatoid arthritis and this case was a female.

3 cases of transudative pleural effusion were found ,1 case each of pleural effusion due to chronic renal failure , cardiac failure and liver cirrhosis.

Table 1: Age and sex wise distribution of pleural effusion

Age group (in years)	Number of patients(Male)	Number of patients(Female)	Number of patients(Total)	Percentage (%)
11-20	02	00	02	2
21-30	08	02	10	10
31-40	26	19	45	45
41-50	15	09	24	24
51-60	06	05	11	11
>60	05	03	08	8
Total	62	38	100	100

Table 2: Distribution of pleural effusion according to etiology

Effusion Type	Etiology	Male	Female	Number of cases
Exudative effusion(97% cases)	Tuberculosis	52	30	82
	Adenocarcinoma of lung(Malignant)	07	01	08
	Carcinoma breast(Malignant)	00	02	02
	Carcinoma Ovary(Malignant)	00	01	01
	Lymphoma(Malignant)	00	01	01
	Parapneumonic effusion	01	01	02
	Rheumatoid Arthritis	00	01	01
Transudative Effusion(3% cases)	Cardiac failure	01	00	01
	Liver cirrhosis	01	00	01
	Chronic renal failure	00	01	01
	Total	62	38	100

Discussion:

The full work-up for pleural effusion include :Physical and chemical examination , Chest X-ray, followed by an evaluation by thoracentesis and pleural fluid cytology and if needed microbiological analysis can determine the cause of pleural effusion. A thoracentesis is indicated if a clinically significant pleural effusion is present that is radiographically at least 10 mm thick. Pleural fluid accumulations can be further evaluated by gross appearance, clinical microscopy, cytopathologic findings, microbiology, pH, tumor markers, and other chemical studies.

Differentiating whether it is exudative pleural effusion or transudative pleural effusion is essential in determining the underlying pathophysiology and subsequent management. Light's criteria serve as a reference standard for determining whether the pleural effusion is exudative or transudative. Exudative effusion is diagnosed if one or more of the following criteria are met:

- Pleural fluid protein/serum protein ratio of more than 0.5
- Pleural fluid LDH/serum LDH ratio of more than 0.6
- Pleural fluid LDH is more than two-thirds of the upper limit of the normal serum LDH value [1] [5]

If none of these criteria are met, the fluid is considered transudative. [6]

Our study found Tuberculosis to be the most common cause of pleural effusion in Firozabad region(82%) followed by malignant pleural effusions (12%) among which most common cause was Adenocarcinoma lung followed by Carcinoma breast ,followed Carcinoma ovary and B-cell Acute lymphoblastic Lymphoma. The third most common cause was found to be parapneumonic effusion (2%) followed by Rheumatoid arthritis(1%).

3 cases of transudative pleural effusion were found of which 1 case each were of pleural effusion due to chronic renal failure ,cardiac failure and liver cirrhosis.

We found male preponderance in pleural effusions due to TB as well as in pleural effusions in lung carcinoma cases(62% males vs 38% females) ,the male:female ratio being 1.63:1. The habit of smoking being more common in males may be the reason behind higher incidence of pleural effusions due to carcinoma lung in males. Also , in our study, the most common age group was 31 - 40 years (45%) followed by 41-50 years(24%).

The youngest case was an 11 year old male who had pleural effusion due to TB and oldest case was a 73 years old male who also had pleural effusion due to TB.

Similar findings were also observed in several other studies. Most of the studies conducted in India and Bangladesh found TB to be the most common cause , this may be because of higher prevalence of TB and other infections in these developing countries.

Similar results were obtained by Bar P.K. et al in their study in which the most common cause of pleural effusion was found to be tuberculosis (64.67%), followed by malignancy (14.67%), parapneumonic effusion (7.33%)[7] .They also found maximum occurrence in 31-40 years as was observed in the present study.

A.S.M. Fazlul Haque et al in their study [8] also found TB to be the most common cause of pleural effusion ,but their study found second most common cause to be parapneumonic effusions. They also found male preponderance (57.31% vs 42.68%) ,the male : female ratio being 1.34:1. Age group more than 60 years was most common in their study which is different from our study.

In a study by Sharma et al [9],64% cases of pleural effusion were due to Tuberculosis and male preponderance was found similar to our study (Male:Female ratio of 37:11).

Parikh P. et al in a similar study [10] , found results similar to our study with most common age group being 31-40 years ,male predominance (68%) and most of the patients had tuberculous pleural effusion(62%) followed by malignant pleural effusion(18%).

Conclusion:

From the present study we can infer that the most common cause of pleural effusion in Firozabad region is Tuberculosis followed by malignancies and parapneumonic effusion. This highlights the need for measures to reduce TB burden and also the need for increasing awareness among people regarding smoking cessation.

We also deduced the inference that cytological smear analysis along with cell block section study are very effective methods to find out etiology of pleural effusion especially when aided by other clinical, radiological ,hematological, biochemical and microbiological investigations.

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